

Car Selection Problem using Assignment Problem

Dr. Muley Yogesh M^{#1}, Dr. Pandit Bhagwat B^{*2}

^{#1}Department of Mathematics, Kai. Rasika Mahavidyalaya, Deoni (India)

^{*2}Department of Mathematics, Shri Datta Arts, Commerce and science college, Hadgaon (India)

¹yogesh.m.muley@gmail.com

²panditbhagwat51@gmail.com

Abstract — In this paper, we tried to solve real life problem i.e. Car selection problem (by taking information of car details through google) is carried out as per user requirement by using Assignment problem as well Revised one’s Assignment method.

Keywords— Assignment problem, ROA, Car Selection problem, Assignment Problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

Now a day’s car selection as per user requirement is difficult task for us, by using Assignment Problem it is possible to trace one – to – one match of given “users” to “cars”. In this paper we tried to find out ideal solution as possible as real, which will find minimum cost value for cars.

Assignment problem is completely degenerated form of transportation problem. It appears in some decision – making problem. In general, it is concerned with one to one basis when ‘n’ jobs are to be assigned to ‘n’ facilities.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF ASSIGNMENT PROBLEM

		Activity/ Destination					
		A ₁	A ₂	⋯	A _n	Availability	
Resource	R ₁	(C ₁₁	C ₁₂	⋯	C _{1n})	1
	R ₂	C ₂₁	C ₂₂	⋯	C _{2n}	1	
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	
	R _n	C _{n1}	C _{n2}	⋯	C _{nn})	1	
Requirement		1	1	⋯	1		

Let (X_{ij}) denote the assignment of ith resources to jth activities such that,

$$X_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if resource } i \text{ is assigned to activity } j. \\ 0; & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then the mathematical formulation of the assignment problem is,

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n C_{ij} X_{ij} \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

Subject to the constraints,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n X_{ij} = 1 \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij} = 1 : X_{ij} = 0 \text{ or } 1 \quad \dots\dots(2)$$

for all i = 1,2,...,n and j = 1,2,...,n.

III. REVISED ONES ASSIGNMENT METHOD (ROA) FOR SOLVING ASSIGNMENT PROBLEM [1],[2], [3].

To solve car selection problem, we have analyse car data as per user requirement i.e. car cc, mileage, ground clearance etc. After that data is converted into numbers using given credit points and lastly by applying ROA method we tried to find optimum solution.

Now, consider the assignment matrix where is the cost or effectiveness of assigning i^{th} machine.

$$\begin{matrix} & 1 & 2 & \dots & n \\ \begin{matrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ n \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & \dots & C_{1n} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & \dots & C_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{n1} & C_{n2} & \dots & C_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

The algorithm is as follows.

Step 1

Find maximum element from each row (say a_i), and note it on RHS of the matrix

$$\begin{matrix} & 1 & 2 & \dots & n \\ \begin{pmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & \dots & C_{1n} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & \dots & C_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{n1} & C_{n2} & \dots & C_{nn} \end{pmatrix} & \begin{matrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \end{matrix} \end{matrix}$$

Then divide a_i to each corresponding row, hence at least one ones form in each row. If one is identical for each row and column then do assignment. Otherwise go for step 2.

Step 2

Similarly, for column find max element from each column (say b_j), and note it down of the matrix. These operation will create one ones in each column, If one is identical for each row and column then do assignment. 2Make assignment in terms of ones. If no feasible assignment can be achieved from step (1) and (2) then go to step 3.

$$\begin{matrix} & 1 & 2 & \dots & n \\ \begin{matrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ \vdots \\ n \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} C_{11}/a_1 & C_{12}/a_1 & \dots & C_{1n}/a_1 \\ C_{21}/a_2 & C_{22}/a_2 & \dots & C_{2n}/a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{n1}/a_n & C_{n2}/a_n & \dots & C_{nn}/a_n \end{pmatrix} \\ & \begin{matrix} b_1 & b_2 & \dots & b_n \end{matrix} \end{matrix}$$

Step 3

Cover all ones of the matrix by drawing minimum number of lines. If $n <$ max number of rows or column then assignment is not possible, while n is equal to max number of rows or column then complete assignment is possible.

Step 4

In case step 3 is fail or complete assignment is not possible, then select max element (say d_{ij}) from drawn uncovered lines of the above matrix. divide by d_{ij} from each element of drawn uncovered lines, thus create new one ones in the matrix. If still assignment fail to optimize solution, the repeat step 3 and 4.

(To assign one we have add Step 5 which is mentioned below.)

Step 5 (Ghadle and Muley Rule)

- For minimization problem select max number from calculated matrix and write it on RHS as well as bottom side.
- To assign one, start from min number of columns (bottom side) and select ones.

- If there are more than one ones in any column then ignore temporarily, and give last priority to that column.
- If still there are identical ones in column then give the priority to max number of rows (RHS).
- If there are more than one ones in any row then give first come priority.

and Vice - versa

Priority rule

One question arises here. What to do with non square matrix? To make square, a non square matrix, we add one artificial row or column which all elements are one. Thus we solve the problem with the new matrix, by using the new method. The matrix after performing the steps reduces to a matrix which has ones in each rows and columns. So, the optimal assignment has been reached.

IV. APPLICATIONS: CAR SELECTION PROBLEM

	Particulars\ Users	General	City	Long drive	Tourist
		2- 3.99 lac	4 - 5.99 lac	6 - 7.99 lac	8 -9.99 lac
CAR PRICE	2 lakh	5	0	0	0
	3 lakh	4	0	0	0
	4 lakh	3	5	0	0
	5 lakh	0	4	0	0
	6 lakh	0	3	5	0
	7 - 8lakh	0	0	4	5
	9 lakh - Above	0	0	0	4
	BODY TYPE	HATCHBACK	3	3	2
SEDAN		0	2	3	2
SUV		0	0	0	3
CC	700 - 999	3	2	0	0
	1000 -1299	0	3	2	2
	1300 - 1599	0	0	3	3
	1600 - above	0	0	4	4
	Mileage	12 - 14 KMPL	1	1	1
	14 - 16 KMPL	2	2	2	2
	16 - 18 KMPL	3	3	3	3
	18 -20 KMPL	4	4	4	4
Ground	160 - 169	1	1	1	1
	170 - 179	2	2	2	2
	180 - 200	3	3	3	3

Particulars	Credit Points
Essential	5
Fairly High	4
High	3
Moderate	2
Low	1
Fairly Low	0

In the above table specific credit points are mentioned as per their types and * vehicle details are given at the last where A1, A2 and so on are the variable names given to each car, finally by adding all credit point for each car the table is shown as follows,

By using Revised Ones Assignment Method (ROA) for Solving Assignment Problem the final solution obtained was,

	Use \ Model	A1	A2	A3	A4	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10
User 1	General	16	15	14	15	13	10	9	13	12	6	14	6	10	7
user 2	City	10	10	9	10	14	15	14	14	13	13	15	13	13	14
User 3	Long Drive	7	7	6	7	6	8	7	6	5	8	7	7	6	8
User 4	Tourist	5	5	4	5	4	6	5	4	3	7	5	5	4	6

	Use \ Model	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
User1	General	7	3	7	5	5	7	4	5	5	3	3	4	6	6	5	3	5	3	3
user 2	City	13	8	13	8	13	13	9	7	5	5	5	9	9	9	5	8	7	5	5
User 3	Long Drive	13	14	13	12	15	13	13	15	12	13	13	13	11	11	12	14	11	9	9
User 4	Tourist	6	8	6	5	9	6	13	15	16	13	13	13	10	10	16	14	14	12	12

The ideal solution for minimal cost for cars (User 1, A1), (User 2, B2), (User 3, C5), (User 4, C9).

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a Revised Ones Assignment Method (ROA) used to solve car selection problem using assignment problem. This method can be used for maximize as well as minimized objective functions.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Hadi Basirzadeh, , *Ones Assignment Method for solving Assignment Problems*, Applied Mathematical Sciences, No. 47, 2345-2355. Vol. 6, 2012.
- [2] Shweta singh, G.C.Dubey, Rajesh Shrivastava, *A Comparative Analysis of Assignment Problem*, IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN), ISSN: 2250-3021, Volume 2, Issue 8, 01-15, August 2012.
- [3] Ghadle Kirtiwant P, Muley Yogesh M, *Revised Ones Assignment Method for Solving Assignment Problem*, Journal of Statistics and Mathematics, ISSN: 0976-8807 & E-ISSN: 0976-8815, Volume 4, Issue 1, 147-150, 2013.

* VI. VEHICLE DETAILS

The given vehicle information is up to 2014-15 and price of vehicle may be vary, this problem is choose only practical problem solving purpose.

Version	Maruti Suzuki 800 AC BS-III	Maruti Suzuki Alto 800 VXi Airbag	Maruti Suzuki Alto K10 VXi	Hyundai Eon Magna +	Chevrolet Spark LT 1.0 BS 4	Hyundai Santro Xing GLS	Maruti Suzuki Alto 800 LXI CNG	Maruti Suzuki Zen Estilo VXi (ABS) BS-IV	Maruti Suzuki Wagon R 1.0 MC VXi (ABS-Airbag)	Tata Indigo eCS GLS	Maruti Suzuki A Star AUTOMATIC
Ex-Showroom Price (Mumbai) in	255397	354793	357940	375907	406529	410096	381175	460465	468369	478737	488197
Body Type	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Sedan	Hatchback
Segment	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	B	B	C	A
Displacement (cc)	796	796	998	814	995	1068	796	998	998	1193	998
Mileage (City/Highway in KMPL)	16/18	18/20	16/18	16/18	14/16	14/17	18/20	16/18	14/16	13/15	16/18
Ground Clearance (mm)	170	160	160	170	170	172	160	165	165	165	170
	A 1	A 2	A 3	A 4	B 1	B 2	B 3	B 4	B 5	B 6	B 7

Version	Ford Figo Duratec Petrol Titanium 1.2	Chevrolet Beat 1.2 LT Opt Petrol	Honda Brio VX MT	Maruti Suzuki Swift ZXI	Tata Indigo eCS VX CR4 BS4	Hyundai i10 Asta 1.2 AT WS GLS Kappa with Sunroof	Skoda Fabia Elegance 1.6 MPI	Chevrolet Sail LT ABS Petrol	Honda Jazz X	Maruti Suzuki New Swift Dzire Automatic	Toyota Etios V SP
Ex-Showroom Price (Mumbai) in	511464	537226	567590	609737	616126	645070	669816	673185	696290	704125	704773
Body Type	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Hatchback	Sedan	Hatchback	Hatchback	Sedan	Hatchback	Sedan	Sedan
Segment	C	B	B	B	B	B	C	B	C	B	C
Displacement (cc)	1196	936	1198	1197	1396	1197	1598	1199	1198	1197	1496
Mileage (City/Highway in KMPL)	14-Dec	14/16	16/18	14/16	13/15	14/18	14/16	16/18	16-Dec	14/16	15/17
Ground Clearance (mm)	168	175	165	170	165	165	158	174	160	170	170
	B 8	B 9	B 10	C 1	C 2	C 3	C 4	C 5	C 6	C 7	C 8

Version	Toyota Etios V SP	Maruti Suzuki Ertiga VXI BS IV	Chevrolet Aveo CNG 1.4	Maruti Suzuki Ritz MC VDI ABS	Chevrolet Aveo LT 1.4 ABS BS4	Maruti Suzuki Swift VDI	Maruti Suzuki New Swift DZire LDI	Tata Manza GEX Safire90 BS-IV	Honda Amaze VX AT Petrol	Volkswagen Polo GT TSI	Hyundai i20 Sportz AT Petrol
Ex-Showroom Price (Mumbai) in	704773	709418	620828	620833	745370	640506	641350	773832	800292	803494	825471
Body Type	Sedan	SUV	Sedan	Hatchback	Sedan	Hatchback	Sedan	Sedan	Sedan	Hatchback	Hatchback
Segment	C	C	A	C	C	B	B	C	B	B	C
Displacement (cc)	1496	1373	1399	1248	1399	1248	1248	1368	1198	1197	1197
Mileage (City/Highway in KMPL)	15/17	14/16	14-Dec	18/20	14/16	16/18	16/18	13/15	15/17	14/16	14/16
Ground Clearance (mm)	170	185	180	170	165	170	170	165	165	168	165
	C 8	C 9	C 10	C 11	C 10	C 13	C 14	C 11	D 1	D 2	D 3

Version	Ford EcoSport 1.5 Ti-VCT Titanium (AT) Petrol	Chevrolet Optra Magnum LT 1.6 ABS BS4	Maruti Suzuki SX4 MC ZXI (O)	Skoda Rapid Elegance 1.6 MPI AT	Honda City 1.5 S AT
Ex-Showroom Price (Mumbai) in	886077	890737	935263	956966	970114
Body Type	SUV	Sedan	Sedan	Sedan	Sedan
Segment	B	C	C	D	C
Displacement (cc)	1499	1991	1586	1598	1497
Mileage (City/Highway in KMPL)	13/16	14/16	14/16	14/16	13/15
Ground Clearance (mm)	200	165	180	168	165
	D 4	D 5	D 6	D 7	D 8